

Automated Solar Solutions-Sun Guardian

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Abstract

The use of renewable resources like solar energy is expanding due to the increased demand for electricity and concern about the environmental effects of fossil fuels. The dusty areas where solar energy systems are typically used include tropical nations like India. The dust builds up on the module's front surface and prevents incident sunlight from passing through. If the device remains uncleaned for a month, the power output decreases even more. Dust buildup on every panel in an array significantly limits their ability to generate electricity, therefore they must be kept as tidy as possible. In our work, we created a system that automatically cleans modules in addition to tracking the sun. An LDR was necessary for this system to track the sun. A sliding wiper system has been designed to assist in cleaning solar panels. And also the monitoring system is included in order to monitor the temperature and humidity. The current tracking-cum cleaning technique, monitoring offers about higher energy output than the fixed PV module in terms of regular energy production. This project provides information on the tracking, cleaning & monitoring system combination. This project is being carried out using a microcontroller.

Keywords –Solar panel, tracking, cleaning, monitoring, efficiency.

I. INTRODUCTION

PV systems work most effectively when they remain at a lower temperature, facing the sun directly, and with little to no blockage. Once dust has accumulated on a PV panel's glass, it usually prevents light to reaching the cell, reducing overall efficiency. According to the report, dust deposition at particular settlement densities might be advantageous for PV performance up to a certain limit. Due to the fact that PV panels only contribute a small portion of the visible spectrum to system heat. If the layer for dust thickens, it creates a barrier that prevents the visible spectrum from reaching the PV cell.

The panel needs automatic cleaning and maintenance as a result. There are several aspects that affect dust accumulation. These include the PV panel's inclination, type of setup (standalone or on a tracker), the direction of the wind, the humidity, etc. The main source of energy is the sun. Most renewable energy systems use this as fuel, either directly or indirectly. The photovoltaic system has the greatest potential among all renewable energy sources to displace current energy sources. Semiconductors are used primarily in the construction of the solar panel. Si is utilised in solar panels as a measurement component.

The only method to boost the solar panel's efficiency is by enhancing the amount of light that it receives. The best technique for increasing solar panel efficiency by maintaining the cells aligned with the sun's position is solar trackers. Solar trackers are becoming more and more well-known nowadays as a means to use solar energy as efficiently as possible. It is extremely advised to clean often in order to maximise efficiency. Particularly, the process of dust accumulation and associated effects are influenced by both environmental and design factors. Necessity Eco-friendly energy sources must be used since power prices are rising and people are worried about the negative effects of fossil fuels on the environment.

The solar panels' ability to absorb solar energy is the primary source of solar electricity. Dust buildup on every single panel lowers the panels' ability to generate electricity. We must keep the panel's surface as spotless as possible because of this. Current labor-based cleaning techniques for rooftop solar panels are expensive in terms of both time and energy.

Therefore, we must create an automatic cleaning device that can efficiently clean and move across the glass surfaces of panels.

India's desert regions, such as those in Rajasthan, Gujarat, Madhya Pradesh, etc., are particularly sun energy-rich. The recommended concept of a single axis solar tracker, however, is most suitable for achieving maximum efficiency because the majority of these install their panels in a fixed direction, which greatly effects the solar energy gathered by the panel

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Mohan S[1] An increasingly significant and well-liked renewable energy source is solar energy. We can generate a great deal of energy and raise the effectiveness of solar panels by employing a solar tracking system. The effectiveness of the solar panel is due to its perpendicular relationship to the sun's beams. Although there are less expensive alternatives, the installation fee is high. This article discusses a working solar panel whose design and construction were inspired by the sun's beams. The main control system is an Arduino. The configuration of this device ensures that the LDR sensor will guide the Servo Motor to move the solar panel when it senses sunlight. As a result, the photovoltaic cell is situated in a way where it can receive maximum sunlight. H Vidhya[2] Internet of Things (IoT) is governing our current reality in a variety of ways. The proposed work entails managing solar panels to boost their output. The method for monitoring and maintaining solar panels that uses IoT is described in this study. When the modules are used in a dusty environment, a neat piece of dust appears on the solar panel, trying to lower its effectiveness and productivity since the power it produces in a solar system depends on the amount of light hitting on it. By providing the panel with an appropriate cleaning method, this issue may be prevented. The suggested work uses light intensity diodes to track solar light automatically and steer the panel accordingly. If any dust or debris is found inside the panel, an automatic cleaning mechanism is utilised to remove it. The output power will rise as a result of this method. The controller is coupled to an arrangement that uses suitable sensors to detect dust. The produced prototype will carry out the operation based on the controller's output. Yung Lio[3] The study's main objective is to compare the performance of several axes of low-concentration photovoltaic/thermal (LCPV/T) solar single-axis tracking systems. The east-west (EW), north-south (NS), and southeast 18° (SE-18°) axes are used to organise the orientations of the single-axis tracker LCPV/T systems, accordingly. Through simulation and experimentation, the thermal efficiency of a single-axis tracking device with various axes is discussed. A simulation research demonstrates that throughout the year, the EW tracking device gets the most radiation and generates the most electrical energy. The experimental investigation shows that the system's performance is greatly enhanced by low-concentrating technology. The greatest thermal efficiency attained in the experiment is 68%, while the total thermal efficiency mostly remains between 50% and 70%. Amith Kumar Yadav[4] Nowadays, electricity is a necessity for all humans. There is a need to use the unbounded source of energy as electrical energy persistence expands and increases daily. The use of solar energy may be useful and favourable to a wide range in the present and modern time of power scarcity in India. By using solar energy, you may save a lot of water, air, fossil fuels, and other natural resources that are vital to preserve for future generations and safeguard the environment from climate change, acid rain, greenhouse gas effects, etc. Maximising solar array systems' productivity and financial viability is necessary to produce solar energy more widely. The presence of dirt, wetness, and the extreme intensity of sunlight on the panel surface have all been taken into account when estimating the productivity and cost-effectiveness of PV panels. Shivagami P[5] The expense of the equipment of renewable energy systems, notably solar photovoltaic systems, is reduced via global melioration of technology. People search for alternate energy sources as a result of depleting resources and rising energy demand. Therefore, it becomes crucial to improve the panels' ability to convert energy. Internet of Things (IoT) technology aids in boosting energy efficiency. IoT has developed into a potent facilitator in this digital age because it affects how people utilise the internet to offer solutions to raise their level of living. IoT combines the digital and physical worlds by enabling sensing and communication equipment to interact with one another in a variety of ways to cater to the demands of the individual users. Md Rawshan Habib[6] A solar panel's surface is sensitive to collected dust. As dust builds up, the solar panel's efficiency gradually declines. In this work, a dust removal system for solar panels built on an Arduino platform is conceived and constructed. The suggested solar panel cleaning is automated, waterless, and cost-effective. This system uses a two-step mechanism that consists of a wiper to remove dust off the panel surface and an exhaust fan that serves as an air blower. The wiper is propelled by a dc motor. Since the arrangement does not require water for cleaning solar panels, waste water is avoided, and it works well in desert regions. Md Masud Ali Shah[7] The Internet of Things (IoT) is used extensively in industrial automation, smart energy monitoring, and a number of other applications. IoT devices are installed at various phases of the Smart Grid (SG) to monitor and regulate grid statistics for dependable and effective electricity distribution. Although there are numerous advantages to integrating IoT in the SG domain, it still faces some

difficulties that must be overcome for the grid to operate effectively. This article begins by giving an overview of the SG and IoT-based SG systems. This project outlines a power monitoring system built on the Internet of Things (IoT) that can measure and analyse electrical characteristics including current, voltage, active power, and load energy usage. The internet of things-based software programme "Thing Speak" is used to gather real-time electrical data from customers. Karam Charafedine[8] The world's main energy sources are starting to disappear, making the need to discover substitutes urgent and essential. Alternative energy sources are now the preferred option for a bright future and a healthy environment. As a result, solar energy is regarded as one of the most significant renewable energy sources. This study describes a moving solar panel and two stepper motor-based automated sun tracking system. The solar panel must always track the sun's movement in order for the reflective surface of the photovoltaic cells to be straight to the sunlight, which is necessary in order to harvest additional energy from the sun. Using a C++ programme, the solar panel's orientation with the sun is accomplished. David L[9] The methods to optimize the

III. PROPOSED SYSTEM

In this implementation we are implementing automatic system. We use different types of components to perform Sun tracking and Cleaning of PV modules. The main components that will be used are Micro-controller, LDR, DC motor, motor driver, cleaning wiper, Solar panel. The control of both the systems are performed separately by using Atmega328 Microcontroller.

3.1 Tracking section

Fig.3.1 Block diagram of tracking system

In tracking part the solar panel will track the sun light and it will automatically move in sun direction. Here we interfacing LDR sensor with microcontroller. Based on sun light the internal resistance of LDR getting change. Based on this resistance the LDR is generating different voltage level according to sun light. The microcontroller will get signal from LDR and based on LDR signal the microcontroller will trigger to motor driver part. The motor driver will start the motor and stop the motor based on trigger signal by microcontroller.

3.2 Cleaning section

Fig. 3.2 Block diagram of cleaning system

In cleaning section, the mechanism for cleaning is depends on microcontroller. A start key is interfaced with microcontroller pin. once user will press the start key for cleaning system. Microcontroller will send a trigger signal to motor driver circuit. In this section the motor connected with cleaning wiper. Two sensor is interfaced at the end of panel. That will make it more advance system. That sensor will detect the wiper is reached on end of panel or not. So wiper will not move more then that limit.

3.3 Monitoring section

Fig. 3.3 Block diagram of monitoring section

Many countries are now looking for alternative sources of energy to lessen their reliance upon fossil based fuels due to the rising cost of fossil fuels, the burning of fuels like coal, global warming, and severe weather conditions. One of the foremost promising forms of clean energy now being employed in the globe to help satisfy the growing need for electric power is solar energy. Sunshine was collected either directly by employing photovoltaics or indirectly by utilizing concentrated solar energy. Solar power is the conversion of sunshine into electricity. Small and medium-sized applications, ranging from calculators operated by a single solar panel to remote residences operated by an off-grid rooftop photovoltaic system, first used photovoltaics as a power source. As the price of solar energy has decreased, utility scale solar energy stations with several hundred thousands of watts are being built, and there are now millions of connected to the grid solar photovoltaic systems. Solar photovoltaic is developing into a low-cost, low-carbon method to capture solar energy. It is true that both its application and maintenance must get careful consideration if solar power generating is to be utilised. The IOT-based solar monitoring device is suggested to gather and analyze the parameters associated with solar panels in order to forecast performance and ensure electricity output.

The main goal of a PV monitor system is to provide a practical option that continuously shows computer screens or mobile devices the performance of distant energy yields. The user may view the temperature, humidity, and amount of sunlight next to the solar panel.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1 IoT MONITORING OF VARIATIONS IN HUMIDITY

When the air is humid, there is more water vapor in the atmosphere, which can scatter and absorb some of the sunlight before it reaches the solar panels. This can cause a slight reduction in the amount of solar radiation that the solar panels receive, and therefore a decrease in the amount of electricity they generate. Additionally, high humidity is often associated with cloudy or overcast weather, which can have a greater impact on solar energy production than humidity alone.

In fact, some studies have found that solar panels can actually perform better in humid conditions than in very dry conditions, as the humidity can help to reduce the operating temperature of the panels by increasing evaporative cooling. This can help to improve the efficiency of the panels and increase the amount of electricity they produce.

Overall, while humidity can have some effect on the performance of solar panels and solar energy production, it is generally a minor factor compared to other environmental variables such as temperature, solar irradiance, and cloud cover.

4.2 IoT MONITORING OF VARIATIONS IN SOLAR RADIATION

Sunlight is the primary source of energy for solar panels, and the amount and intensity of sunlight can have a significant effect on the performance of solar panels and the amount of solar energy they produce. Numerous research papers have investigated the relationship between sunlight and solar panel performance.

The amount of solar energy produced by a solar panel is directly proportional to the amount of sunlight it receives. This relationship is described by the "solar irradiance" or the amount of solar radiation that reaches a unit of area on the surface of the earth. According to a study published in the journal Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews, a 1% increase in solar irradiance can lead to a 1% increase in solar energy production.

The intensity and angle of sunlight also play a role in solar panel performance. A study published in the Journal of Renewable and Sustainable Energy found that solar panels perform best when the angle of incidence of the sunlight is perpendicular to the panel surface, and that the efficiency of the panel decreases as the angle of incidence deviates from this ideal angle.

A study published in the journal Energy found that shading caused by clouds can reduce solar energy production by up to 75%, while another study published in Solar Energy showed that air pollution can reduce solar irradiance by up to 10%.

4.3 IoT MONITORING OF VARIATIONS IN TEMPERATURE

Temperature can also have an impact on solar panel performance, as higher temperatures can cause a decrease in panel efficiency. A study published in the journal Solar Energy found that solar panel efficiency can decrease by up to 0.5% for every degree Celsius increase in temperature above 25°C. In summary, sunlight is a critical factor in the performance of solar panels and the amount of solar energy they produce. The amount, intensity, angle, and quality of sunlight can all impact solar panel efficiency, and numerous research papers have investigated these relationships in detail.

Temperature can affect the performance of solar panels and the amount of solar energy they produce in several ways. Generally, the efficiency of solar panels decreases as temperature increases, which can cause a decrease in the amount of electricity they produce. Some of the ways temperature affects solar energy are:

Temperature coefficient: Each solar panel has a temperature coefficient, which is a measure of how much the panel's efficiency decreases with an increase in temperature. The temperature coefficient typically ranges from -0.2% to -0.5% per degree Celsius, depending on the type of panel. This means that for every degree Celsius increase in temperature above a certain level, the panel's efficiency will decrease by a certain percentage.

Heat loss: When solar panels become hot, they lose energy due to heat loss. This can cause a decrease in efficiency and an overall decrease in the amount of electricity produced.

Voltage drop: As the temperature of the solar panel increases, the voltage output of the panel decreases. This can cause a decrease in the overall power output of the panel and can lead to a loss of energy.

Cooling systems: In some cases, solar panels may be equipped with cooling systems to prevent them from overheating. These cooling systems can help to maintain the efficiency of the panels and increase the amount of energy they produce. Temperature can have a significant impact on the performance of solar panels and the amount of solar energy they produce. As temperature increases, the efficiency of solar panels decreases, which can cause a decrease in the overall amount of electricity produced. However, with proper cooling systems and other measures, it is possible to minimize the effects of temperature on solar energy production.

VI. CONCLUSION

This project is for a tracking and cleaning device for solar panels. Although an array structure consists of several solar panels lined up in a row, this system can only be used for only one solar panel. In order to boost efficiency, this system may also be used with array systems, which is very helpful. The implemented prototype can easily mount to another array because it is detachable. The above system is a single axis tracking system that rotates its axis automatically in response to a change in motor direction, and may be maintained inclined either north or south to maximise the energy produced by the solar panel. If this sensor is operating, we may clean the panel autonomously a number of times and add a revolving wiper to the system. As a further modification, we can also use another sensor to provide information regarding ambient saturation on the panel. Finally, all of the development projects were effective in carrying out both operations following this.

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